

Array Position Optimisation for Compressed Sensing MIMO Radar based on Mutual Coherence Minimisation

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Abstract—In this paper, an optimization methodology for re-positioning antenna elements of a collocated Compressed Sensing (CS) based Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) radar, to improve target detection performance, by minimizing the mutual coherence of the associated sensing matrix has been suggested. We initialize the problem as a mutual coherence of the sensing matrix resulting from a simple 3Tx/4Rx Uniform Linear Array (ULA) restricted by an array aperture of specified size, and then reposition the elements within the restricted aperture such that the value of mutual coherence reduces. The optimization problem is formulated as minimizing the l_∞ norm of the Gramian of the associated sensing matrix, the global optimization solver simulated annealing is considered to solve the nonconvex problem. The optimized array's performance is evaluated against a ULA, Co-prime array, and Sparse array by comparing metrics such as the probability of perfect reconstruction (Recovery percentage) and Recovery error (root mean square error (rmse)) for scenes with multiple targets and different SNR values, using Monte Carlo simulations. The study demonstrates the methodology to generate a random array, which results in low mutual coherence of its respective sensing matrix, which consequently results in improved performance of the CS-MIMO radar.

Index Terms—MIMO, Compressed sensing, Mutual coherence, Sensing matrix design, Random array

I. INTRODUCTION

Collocated MIMO radars consist of closed spaced antenna elements, such that all transmitter and receiver pairs view a target at nearly the same angle. Collocated MIMO radars provide various advantages such as improved angular resolution, better parameter identifiability and interference rejection capabilities [1]. When concerning angular resolution, the arrangement of antenna elements plays a significant role, as it directly relates to the virtual array synthesized. A detailed review of the different types of array configuration can be found in [3]. In recent years, the application of Compressed Sensing (CS) to MIMO radars has gained interest, both from performance and design perspectives. When considering design, the possibilities to design sparse arrays which have lesser number of elements compared to Uniform Linear arrays (ULA), but still provide the same results, are of great interest. When concerning performance, the possibilities to improve the reconstruction capabilities of MIMO radar with same number elements but with a different arrangement are of great interest.

When considering the case of performance of CS MIMO radars, the successful recovery of targets from a scene of noisy

measurements is based on two assumptions, a) the scene is sparse, meaning the number of estimated targets must be far less than the number of radar cells; this assumption in most cases is valid [5]. The second criterion is that the associated sensing matrix must satisfy the Restricted Isometric Property (RIP) [19]. The RIP provides guarantee for the recovery performance for a considered Sensing matrix. Sadly validating the RIP is an NP hard problem and this theoretical metric is not valuable for practical purposes. An alternative to the RIP is the mutual coherence, which is given by

$$\mu(\mathbf{A}) \triangleq \max_{i \neq j} \frac{|\mathbf{a}_i^H \mathbf{a}_j|}{\|\mathbf{a}_i\| \|\mathbf{a}_j\|} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the sensing matrix, \mathbf{a}_i and \mathbf{a}_j are columns of \mathbf{A} . A lower $\mu(\mathbf{A})$, indicates well distinguishable column pairs, thus better reconstruction. For MIMO radar systems the sensing matrix is a function of the system configuration, mainly array geometry and correlation properties of the transmitted waveform [5]–[8]. The focus of this study will be towards minimizing the mutual coherence of a sensing by repositioning the Tx and Rx elements on fixed aperture of a collocated CS MIMO radar.

Minimizing the mutual coherence of a sensing matrix to achieve better performance by array optimisation has been attempted before. The authors in [9] consider, the problem of sensor selection for source detection using planar arrays in a CS-based framework which has been addressed through mutual coherence minimization. In [11], the authors approach the antenna placement for direction of arrival (DOA) estimation using a CS-based collocated MIMO radar with a reduced number of elements, by bounding the coherence of the resulting matrix. In [12], [13], the authors have suggested a sparse array design based on optimising the Ambiguity function using global optimiser and have conducted an extensive study on comparing arrays of different number of elements and different field of views. The authors in [14] consider the task of antenna placement for a CS-based collocated MIMO radar with linear arrays; they obtain a probability distribution for selecting the antenna locations and also suggest an antenna selection procedure from the distribution that yields an array configuration that results in a sensing matrix of low mutual coherence. As it can be seen, almost all studies approach the

array design problem as a thinning of dense array or selection weights corresponding to positions, which yield low mutual coherence.

In our study, we focus on the **repositioning** of the array elements from an initial ULA configuration of fixed Tx and Rx elements, over a predefined aperture. We aggressively minimize $\|\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{I}\|_\infty$ which is the maximum value mutual coherence, using a global optimizer, in contrast to $\|\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{I}\|_2$. The result of this method is a random array, meaning the spacing between elements can be considered as a random variable.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the MIMO system model is discussed. The optimization problem related to antenna repositioning based on mutual coherence minimization is formulated in Section 3. Section 4, discusses the simulation results and performance metrics, and finally Section 5, concludes with the findings of the study.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider a MIMO radar with a fixed aperture of $h\lambda$ within which the \mathbf{L} transmitting and \mathbf{Q} receiving elements are uniformly placed forming a ULA configuration along the x axis. The position of Tx and Rx antenna elements are given by

$$\begin{aligned} x_{t,i} &= (i-1)d_T, \forall i = 1, \dots, L \\ x_{r,j} &= (j-1)d_R, \forall j = 1, \dots, Q \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $d_T = Q \times \lambda/2$ & $d_R = \lambda/2$, the arrangement of the Tx and Rx elements constitute a virtual MIMO aperture $V = (L-1)d_T + (Q-1)d_R$, with LQ elements equally spaced at $\lambda/2$. Thus, the signal model for the transmit and receive array responses at an angle θ are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a}_T(u) &= \left[e^{jk_0 \mathbf{x}_{t,1} u}, \dots, e^{jk_0 \mathbf{x}_{t,L} u} \right]^T \\ \mathbf{a}_R(u) &= \left[e^{jk_0 \mathbf{x}_{r,1} u}, \dots, e^{jk_0 \mathbf{x}_{r,Q} u} \right]^T \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where, k_0 is the wavenumber and $u = \cos(\theta)$ is the direction cosine, with θ the azimuth angle corresponding to the direction of arrival (DOA) of a target in the far field of the radar. According to the MIMO requirement [1], consider that each Tx element transmits an independent waveform with good autocorrelation and cross-correlation properties; in our case, we consider a Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) transmission strategy where a baseband signal is encoded with orthogonal sequences such as Gold or Hadamard codes [15], this allows simultaneous transmissions on Tx channels, thus the waveform matrix is given by

$$\mathbf{X}_{K \times L} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_L] \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{x}_i is the baseband signal transmitted by the i^{th} Tx antenna and K is the number of samples.

Let the radiated signals be incident on a scene with G targets and be received by the Q receivers; the received signal is thus given by

$$\mathbf{s}_Q(t) = \sum_{g=1}^G \beta_g \mathbf{a}_R(\theta_g) \mathbf{a}_T(\theta_g)^T \mathbf{X}_g \quad (5)$$

where θ_g corresponds to the angular parameters of the target and \mathbf{X}_g refers to the matrix of delayed version of the signal due to the g targets.

Consider the Rx signal to be sampled at a sub-Nyquist frequency. The M_t fast time samples are used to calculate the range values from R_0 to $R_0 + r_{nr} \Delta r$, where r_{nr} corresponds to each range bin and Δr the range resolution. Hence, it is calculated as $r_{nr} = 1 - K \dots M_t - 1$ and the total number of range bins is $N_r = M_t + K - 1$.

The angular grid is represented by equally spaced N_u points corresponding to the antenna aperture, characterized by the number of virtual receiver elements. Thus $u_{nu} = \cos(nu)$, represents the direction cosine for the point nu on the angular grid. Thus the discretized version of the received signal for a single point target (ignoring slow time) at each q^{th} receiver and m_t instance is given by

$$\begin{aligned} s(m_t, q, nr, nu) &= \beta \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \exp\{jk_0(u_{nu}(p_q + v_l))\} \\ &\quad \times \mathbf{X}(l, k) \delta(k - (m_t - nr)) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where nr, nu are the indexes corresponding to the range and angle bin occupied by the target with complex amplitude β , respectively.

The sensing matrix for the MIMO radar can be considered as a dictionary of all possible range and angular hypotheses observed by Q receivers from code sequences of length K radiated from L transmitters given by $A \in M \times N$. Consider the total number of unknowns $N = N_r \times N_u$ the total number of measurements $M = M_t \times Q$. Therefore, each column index is given by $n = nr + (nu-1)N_r$ and each row index is given by $m = m_t + (q-1)M_t$, each code index for the vectorized waveform matrix \mathbf{X} is given by $h = k + (l-1)K$, thus the coefficients of the sensing matrix a_{mn} are given by

$$\begin{aligned} a_{mn} &= \sum_h \exp\{jk_0(u_{nu}(n)(p_q(m) + v_l(h)))\} \\ &\quad \times \mathbf{X}(L(h), K(h)) \delta(K(h) - (m_t(m) - nr(n))) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Hence, for each receiver and we have a matrix \mathbf{A}_{Q, N_u} with coefficients as given in equation (6), which are stacked together. \mathbf{A} , is hence given by

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{1,1} & \dots & \mathbf{A}_{1,N_u} \\ \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{A}_{Q,1} & \dots & \mathbf{A}_{Q,N_u} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

From equation (8) it is clear that the sensing matrix is dependent on the correlation property of the waveforms and the positions of the virtual array elements, which in turn depends on the position of the physical Tx and Rx elements.

In order to isolate the effects of the antenna elements, we consider one specific range bin corresponding to the sensing

matrix in equation (8). As a result, the reduced sensing matrix is given by $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = [\psi_1, \dots, \psi_{Nu}]$, such that each column corresponds to

$$\psi_{nu} = \mathbf{a}_R(nu) \otimes \mathbf{X}\mathbf{a}_T(nu), \forall nu = 1, \dots, Nu \quad (9)$$

where ψ_{nu} is the hypothesis that corresponds to the nu^{th} angular bin. Thus, the CS formulation of DoA estimation can be given by

$$\mathbf{y} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{s} is the sparse vector and \mathbf{y} is the measurement vector and $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ is the angular sensing matrix at a specific range bin. The recovery process for estimating target ranges can be performed individually for each range bin or simultaneously using the model in equation (7). In this study, the DoA estimation is called out using the Basis Pursuit Denoising algorithm as in [17].

Remark

In above introduced system model, we consider omnidirectional array antennas operating under ideal conditions. Effects related to mutual coupling between the antenna can be neglected as the average inter-element spacing is greater than 2λ . However, the effects of mutual coupling can be easily factored into the system model via incorporating mutual coupling matrices [14].

III. OPTIMIZATION METHODOLOGY

As explained previously, the mutual coherence of the sensing matrix for a MIMO system depends on the antenna positions and waveform correlations. To limit the effects to antenna positions, we consider the reduced sensing matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$. The objective, is to find the optimum combination of position vectors $\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l$ representing the placement of the Rx and Tx antennas, restricted over an aperture of $h\lambda$, such that the resulting virtual array and its corresponding sensing matrix would have uniquely distinguishable column pairs, i.e. low mutual coherence. As a design requirement we consider the array elements to be placed at a minimum separation of $\lambda/4$, and the optimization problem is thus formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l, \tilde{\mathbf{A}}} \quad & \mu(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \tilde{\mathbf{A}} = f(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l) \\ & \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{p}_q + \sum_{q=1}^Q \mathbf{v}_l \leq h\lambda \\ & \mathbf{p}_q \in [0, h\lambda] \\ & \mathbf{v}_l \in [0, h\lambda] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where,

$$\mu(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) \triangleq \max_{i \neq j} \frac{|\psi_i(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l)^H \psi_j(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l)|}{\|\psi_i(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l)\| \|\psi_j(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l)\|} \quad (12)$$

in which, $\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l$ are the optimised parameters. Before the problem in (12) can be solved, we consider some assumptions and modifications to reduce the computation load. Firstly,

consider that the transmitted waveform is perfectly orthogonal, as the focus of the study is on finding the optimum position of the array elements, we eliminate any effect from the waveform correlation properties, therefore $\mathbf{X}^H \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{I}$. Secondly, the numerator in (12), can be efficiently calculated using the Gram matrix, which is given by $G = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^H \tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ represent the sensing matrix with normalized columns. Since the gram matrix is Hermitian, the set of values which correspond to the mutual coherence (inner product of non-similar columns) can taken as the upper triangular elements, excluding the principal diagonal elements (p.d.e). Additionally, since the secondary diagonals around the p.d.e, represent the width main lobe of the array response, we consider a caliber term to avoid penalizing the main lobe, this ensures focus on the sidelobes. The caliber is calculated as a half power beam width based on the aperture of synthesized, which is adapted from [12], and can be taken as the number of c secondary diagonals to be excluded.

The resulting mutual coherence values can be a represented as a vector $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{C}^{(N-c)(N-c-1)/2}$, where c is the number of secondary diagonals excluded. The objective thus now reduces to minimize the maximum value of \mathbf{z} by rearranging $\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l$ within the predefined aperture $h\lambda$, thus the problem is re-written as,

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l, \mathbf{z}} \quad & \|\mathbf{z}\|_{\infty} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & z_{i,j} = \frac{|\psi_i(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l)^H \psi_j(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l)|}{\|\psi_i(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l)\| \|\psi_j(\mathbf{p}_q, \mathbf{v}_l)\|}, 1 \leq i \neq j \leq N \\ & \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{p}_q + \sum_{q=1}^Q \mathbf{v}_l \leq h\lambda \\ & \mathbf{p}_q \in [0, h\lambda] \\ & \mathbf{v}_l \in [0, h\lambda] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The problem in equation (13), is a non-convex non-linear problem and finding antenna positions is multidimensional and hence cannot be easily solved. Hence, we consider the use of a global optimization solver Simulated annealing [19]. The solution to the optimization problem presents an array configuration chosen for low mutual coherence. The positions in cm are $\mathbf{v}_l = [0, 6.6, 10.12]$ and $\mathbf{p}_q = [0, 2.53, 7.33, 10.12]$. The obtained array scheme is graphically represented in figure 2.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Assuming that a perfect orthogonal sequence is used as transmitting waveform, we consider 3 different array configurations, namely ULA, Co-prime, and a Sparse array arbitrary chosen from the aperture limit. the wavelength is chosen as per automotive standards for a center frequency of 77Ghz. We compare the three candidates against the obtained optimized array, using the metrics:

Fig. 1. Comparison of mutual coherence of sensing matrices for different array configurations, from the subfigure on the left, we can see the histogram of mutual coherence for different array geometries and its comparison to the Welch bound; we see that the optimized array has its mutual coherence values closer to the bound compared to the others, the right subfigure depicts the variation in the sensing matrices via the Gramian bound,

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of input ULA configuration and obtained Optimised array configuration, based on mutual coherence minimisation.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the array AF of the optimized 3T/4Rx array against ULA, Coprime and Sparse array for a target chosen at $\theta = 65$

- **In-coherency** : The mutual coherence of the sensing matrices are represented by histogram of absolute off-diagonal elements of the Gram matrices. The comparison of mutual coherence from different array geometries w.r.t. the Welch bound [18], can be seen in Figure 1. The respective Gram matrices from each configuration have also been presented to illustrate the impact coherence.
- **Ambiguity function (AF)**: The AF is the match filter response for a considered array geometry wrt a test hypothesis of a target and all other possible hypothesis within a considered field of view (Fov) [16], which is given by

$$AF(\theta, \tilde{\theta}) = \frac{|\mathbf{A}(\theta)^H a(\tilde{\theta})|}{L \times Q} \quad (14)$$

where $a(\tilde{\theta})$ is the response of the array at the angle of the test hypothesis angle $\tilde{\theta}$ and $\mathbf{A}(\theta)$ is the matrix of

all possible angular hypotheses in the Fov consideration, L is the number of Tx elements and Q the number of Rx elements. Figure 3 shows the comparison of the test candidates against the optimized array for an angular response at θ .

- **Recovery Percentage** : Recovery percentage can be considered as the ratio between the number of perfect target estimates to the total number of actual targets present for a considered scene. To ensure reliability of the metric, we have conducted Monte Carlo simulations with different number of targets, placed at different angular bins. Figure 4 shows the recovery percentages for sparsity orders $1 \leq K \leq 10$. It can be seen that as the reduction of the mutual coherence directly impacts the reconstruction efficiency of the CS algorithm BPDN, the Optimized array outperforms all the test candidates.

Fig. 4. Recovery percentage versus sparsity (K), where different sparsity order $1 \leq K \leq 10$ over 1000 iteration

- Recovery error** : Recovery error for a given target scene is considered as the error in estimating a target's complex amplitude w.r.t. the amplitudes of a ground truth, which is $\|\hat{\mathbf{a}} - \mathbf{a}\|_2$. The metric is considered under two scenarios, the first when the number of targets in a scene are fixed but are of different signal strengths, SNR values from (-20:1:20) dB as in figure 5 and the second, when the sparsity order is varied for a common SNR value as in figure 6. Both scenarios are evaluated using Monte Carlo simulations for 1000 runs. It can be seen in both cases that the optimized array outperforms the test candidates.

Fig. 5. Comparison of estimation error for K=5, at different SNR cases

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an antenna repositioning scheme for CS-MIMO radar has been suggested, the approach is based on minimizing the mutual coherence of a sensing matrix, so as to improve the reconstruction performance of the CS-MIMO

Fig. 6. Comparison of estimation error for SNR = 0dB, with different number of targets

array in the DOA domain. The reduction in mutual coherence is visually presented using the Gram matrix and its respective histogram of off-diagonal elements. Our results show that the achieved low mutual coherence values directly impact the reconstruction performance of the same CS algorithm. We demonstrate using Monte Carlo simulations, that the optimised 3Tx/4Rx array outperforms other candidate arrays such as ULA, Co-prime and Sparse array with similar number of elements.

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